

HYBRID TOUGHENING OF EPOXY WITH RUBBER AND NANOSILICA PARTICLES: EXPERIMENTS AND MODELLING

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical properties, fracture performance and toughening mechanisms of an anhydride cured epoxy polymer modified by different combinations of preformed core-shell rubber particles (CSR) and nanosilica particles are investigated. Two types of CSR particles, with diameters of 100 nm and 300 nm, are used. The Young's modulus of the epoxy decreased with the increasing weight percentage of CSR particles, but increased with the addition of nanosilica. Both the compressive modulus and yield stress decreased with the increasing CSR particle content; however, the addition of nanosilica led to an increase of the compressive modulus, while the yield stress remained unchanged. The glass transition temperature of the unmodified epoxy was 159 °C and this was unchanged by the addition of CSR particles and nanosilica. The fracture energy increased from 78 J/m² for the unmodified epoxy to 530 J/m² with an addition of 9 wt% of 100 nm diameter CSR particles and to 403 J/m² with an addition of 300 nm diameter CSR particles; this was further enhanced by the addition of nanosilica. CSR particle cavitation was identified as one of the toughening micro-mechanisms through field emission gun scanning electron microscopy (FEG-SEM). The toughening mechanisms of particle-modified epoxies were also investigated through non-linear finite element analyses. The model represents a two-dimensional axisymmetric unit-cell of nanosilica-embedded epoxy under triaxial loading, considering an elastic-plastic response for the epoxy and cohesive interaction between the nanosilica and the epoxy matrix. The model predicts that there is significant plastic deformation of the epoxy before it debonds from the nanosilica, and that both plasticity of the matrix and particle debonding contribute significantly to energy dissipation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxies are thermosetting polymers widely used as structural adhesives, coatings and matrices for fibre-reinforced composites in many engineering applications. They possess relatively high Young's modulus and strength, creep resistance, chemical resistance and high temperature properties. However, cured epoxies have highly cross-linked polymer networks, which make them inherently brittle. This can be overcome by the addition of a second micro-phase (e.g. soft or rigid particles), which can significantly increase the toughness of epoxies [1].

Phase-separating carboxyl-terminated butadiene-acrylonitrile (CTBN) particles are the most commonly used rubber particles to toughen epoxy matrices [1, 2]. More recently, toughness modification by preformed core-shell rubber (CSR) particles has also been investigated [3]. CSR particles have a soft rubber core surrounded by a hard polymer shell. The core imparts impact resistance, and polybutadiene, styrene-butadiene, siloxane and acrylic are the materials most

frequently used as the core [9]. Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) shells are most commonly used and are compatible with the epoxy matrix.

When compared to CSR particles, CTBN particles provide a larger toughening effect but reduce the glass transition temperature of the epoxy, while CSR particles increase the toughness of epoxy without affecting the glass transition temperature. Moreover, the size of CTBN particles is dependent on the curing conditions and therefore it is difficult to control the particle size, whereas the size of CSR particles is pre-determined and is independent of the curing conditions [4]. A disadvantage of both CTBN and CSR particles is that they decrease of the Young's modulus of epoxy matrices.

Rigid particle toughening incorporates micron sized silica, alumina, and (more recently) nanosilica particles in epoxies [5, 6]; this has a positive effect on the toughness as well as on the Young's modulus of epoxy. Hybrid particles, i.e. combining more than one type of particle, have also been used to modify the toughness of epoxies, and detailed work has been reported for hybrid-modified epoxy with nanosilica and CTBN [7, 8]. However, little work has been reported for hybrid-modified epoxies with CSR particles and nanosilica [9], although this combination can increase the toughness of the material without reducing its Young's modulus.

Finite element modelling of the toughening mechanisms of rubber particles and nanosilica has been well reported [10, 11]. Similarly, analytical modelling of toughening mechanisms of rubber particles, nanosilica and hybrid modified epoxies has been well established. However, little work has been reported on the finite element modelling of toughening mechanisms of core-shell rubber particles and hybrid-particle modified epoxies.

The objective of the present work is to investigate experimentally the mechanical properties, fracture performance and toughening mechanisms of an anhydride cured epoxy polymer modified by different combinations of preformed core-shell rubber particles and nanosilica particles. Also, a two-dimensional axisymmetric unit-cell finite element model has been developed to predict the toughening mechanisms of nanosilica reinforced epoxy assuming cohesive interfacial adhesion between the particle and the matrix. Triaxial loading conditions are used to mimic the triaxial stress state ahead of a crack tip. This is the first attempt in the literature to consider a triaxial stress state in two-dimensional modelling of toughening mechanisms of particle-modified epoxies.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Materials

The materials used are listed in Table 1. A diglycidyl ether of bis-phenol A (DGEBA), LY556, epoxy resin was used. This was cross-linked using an accelerated methylhexahydrophthalic acid anhydride, Albidur HE 600. The core-shell rubber particles used in this study are MX156, with a polybutadiene core and PMMA shell, and MX960, with a siloxane core and PMMA shell. The CSR particles are supplied dispersed at 25 wt% in a DGEBA. Nanosilica particles, Nanopox F400, were used to modify epoxies along with CSR particles. The nanosilica particles are supplied dispersed at 40 wt% in a DGEBA resin.

The epoxy formulations manufactured are: unmodified epoxy, epoxies modified with varying weight percentages of CSR particles, and hybrid-modified epoxies containing varying weight percentages of CSR particles and nanosilica particles, see Table 2. The weight percentages of the tougheners were varied and the epoxy equivalent weight of the mixture was calculated. The mixture was then mechanically stirred for 15 min and degassed at 50 °C and -1 atm in a vacuum oven. A stoichiometric amount of the hardener was mixed in, stirred together for 15 min at 60 °C and degassed. The resin mixture was then poured into pre-heated steel gravity moulds and cured at 90 °C for 1 hour, then post-cured at 160 °C for 2 hours (with a ramp rate of 1 °C/min).

Table 1: List of materials used in the study.

Materials	Reference	Supplier	Diameter (nm)	Epoxy equivalent weight, EEW (g/eq)
Epoxy	LY556	Huntsman, UK	-	185
Hardener	Albidur, HE600	Evonik, Germany	-	
CSR particle	MX156	Kaneka, Belgium	Core: 100 [12] Shell: 85 to 115 [12]	243
CSR particle	MX960	Kaneka, Belgium	Core: 300 [12] Shell: 250 to 350 [12]	243
Nanosilica	F400	Evonik, Germany	20 [13]	295

Table 2: Epoxy formulations studied (CSR = core-shell rubber, NS = nanosilica).

		Nanosilica content, wt%				
		0	3	6	9	12
CSR content, wt%	0	unmodified	×	×	×	×
	3	3CSR	3CSR3NS	3CSR6NS	3CSR9NS	3CSR12NS
	6	6CSR	6CSR3NS	6CSR6NS	6CSR9NS	6CSR12NS
	9	9CSR	×	×	9CSR9NS	×

2.2 Mechanical tests

Uniaxial tensile tests were conducted using dumbbell-shaped specimens machined from 3 mm thick epoxy plates according to the ISO 527 standard [14, 15]. Six samples of 25 mm gauge length were prepared for each formulation. The tests were carried out at a displacement rate of 1 mm/min. A clip-on extensometer was used to measure the axial strain. The Young's modulus, E , was calculated from the linear portion of the stress-strain curve in the 0.0005-0.0025 strain range.

Plane strain compression (PSC) tests were carried out to investigate the yield behaviour of the epoxies. The tests were performed at a displacement rate of 0.1 mm/min as described by Williams and Ford [16]. Two specimens of dimensions 3 mm × 40 mm × 40 mm machined from 3 mm thick epoxy plates, for each epoxy formulation were loaded under compression between two 12 mm wide parallel platens. The results obtained were corrected for the compliance of the machine and test rig using the materials testing software Bluehill (Instron, High Wycombe). The values of compressive modulus, yield stress and fracture strain were obtained from the stress/strain curve. The compressive modulus was calculated from the linear portion of the curve in the 0-0.02 strain range.

The fracture energy, G_c , and fracture toughness, K_c , at the initiation of crack growth were determined using the single-edge-notch bending (SENB) test. The tests were conducted according to the ISO 13586 standard [17] at a displacement rate of 1 mm/min. Twelve samples each with a size of

60 mm × 12 mm × 6 mm were machined from 6 mm thick epoxy plates of each formulation, and a sharp pre-crack was introduced by tapping a liquid nitrogen cooled razor blade into the v-notch. The ratio of crack length to specimen depth was within 0.45 to 0.55.

2.3 Fractography

High resolution field emission gun scanning electron microscopy (FEG-SEM) was performed to identify the toughening mechanisms of the CSR particle-modified and hybrid- modified epoxies. The fracture surfaces of the SENB test samples were examined using a Leo 1525 microscope (Carl Zeiss, Germany) equipped with a Gemini column. A 5 kV accelerating voltage was maintained, and all the specimens were sputter-coated with a 10-15 nm thick layer of chromium before taking the images to avoid charging.

2.4 Thermal studies

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was done to measure the glass transition temperature, T_g , of the modified epoxies. A Q800 from TA Instruments, UK was used. Samples of size 60 × 10 × 3 mm³ were tested in double cantilever mode at 1 Hz. A heating rate of 2 °C/min were used within a temperature range of -100 to 200 °C. The storage modulus, loss modulus and $\tan\delta$ were calculated as a function of temperature, and the T_g was determined as the temperature corresponding to the peak of $\tan\delta$.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Mechanical properties

The Young's modulus measured for the unmodified epoxy was 2.87 GPa, which is in good agreement with the values of 2.88 GPa and 2.76 GPa obtained by Chong and Taylor [18] and Masania [8] respectively. The Young's modulus of epoxy decreased with the increase of CSR particle content due to the much lower modulus of the CSR particles compared to the epoxy. However, the addition of nanosilica to the CSR particles-modified epoxies increased the modulus, see Figure 1. The Young's moduli obtained with the addition of MX960 particles are slightly lower than with the addition of a similar amount of MX156 particles, as the MX960 particles have larger core to shell volume ratio.

Figure 1: Young's modulus, E_t , versus nanosilica content for (a) all the MX156 CSR particle-modified epoxies (b) all the MX960 CSR particle-modified epoxies.

The compressive modulus obtained for the unmodified epoxy was 1.94 GPa, in good agreement with the value of 1.81 GPa obtained by Chong and Taylor [18]. The compressive modulus and yield stress decreased with the increase in CSR particle content, as was found for the tensile Young's modulus, see Figure 2. The MX960-modified epoxies have a lower modulus than the MX156-

modified epoxies. The compressive modulus of the CSR particle-modified epoxy increased with the wt% increase of nanosilica particles as in the case of tensile modulus, but the yield stress showed no significant change, suggesting intermediate levels of adhesion [19].

Figure 2: Yield stress, σ_{yc} , versus CSR content.

The true compressive stress versus true strain plots, obtained from the plane strain compression tests clearly show three different deformation regions: i) linear elastic region up to yield point, ii) strain softening region, where the stress decreases with the increase in strain, and iii) strain hardening region, where the stress increases with strain followed by the failure of the epoxies, see Figure 3.

Figure 3: True compressive stress versus true strain plots for (a) 6 wt% MX156 CSR particle- and varying weight percentages of nanosilica-modified epoxies (b) 6 wt% MX960 CSR particle- and varying weight percentages of nanosilica-modified epoxies.

3.2 Fracture energy

The fracture energy and fracture toughness measured for the unmodified epoxy are 78 J/m^2 and $0.49 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ respectively, in good agreement with 77 J/m^2 and $0.51 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ reported by Giannakopoulos et al. [9].

The fracture energy increases significantly with the increase of both types of CSR particle content as shown in Figure 4. It was found that MX156 particles have slightly higher toughening effect than

MX960 particles. The reasons behind this are currently being investigated. The addition of nanosilica particles to the CSR modified epoxies further increased the fracture energy (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Fracture energy versus nanosilica content for (a) 3 wt%, 6 wt% and 9 wt% MX156 CSR particle-modified epoxies (b) 3 wt%, 6 wt% and 9 wt% MX960 CSR particle-modified epoxies.

3.3 Toughening micromechanisms

The fracture surface of unmodified epoxy was found to be smooth and glassy as observed by FEG-SEM, see Figure 5. This implies that no significant plastic deformation of the epoxy occurred, which is typical of a thermoset polymer, and hence a low fracture energy of 78 J/m² was obtained. The micrographs of the fracture surfaces of 6% MX156- and 6% MX960-modified epoxies are shown in Figure 6 and the micrographs of the fracture surfaces of 6% MX156 9% nanosilica- and 6% MX960 9% nanosilica-modified epoxies are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 5: FEG-SEM image of fracture surface for unmodified epoxy.

It was found that the fracture surface of the 6CSR epoxy is rougher than the unmodified epoxy, and that of 6CSR9NS epoxy is even rougher. The dark circular features seen on the surfaces of both the 6CSR epoxy and 6CSR9NS epoxy are cavitated CSR particles, which formed voids in the epoxy matrix. Cavitation is a major toughening mechanism by CSR particles. For the 6CSR9NS modified epoxy, nanosilica particles are identified in the fracture surface. No evidence of nanosilica debonding with void growth in the epoxy matrix was found.

Figure 6: FEG-SEM image of fracture surface for (a) 6 wt% MX156- and (b) 6 wt% MX960-modified epoxies. White arrows show the direction of crack-propagation.

Figure 7: FEG-SEM image of fracture surface for (a) 6 wt% MX156 CSR particle- and 9 wt% nanosilica-modified epoxies (b) 6 wt% MX960 CSR particle- and 9 wt% nanosilica-modified epoxies. White arrows show the direction of crack-propagation.

3.4 Glass transition temperature

The glass transition temperature of unmodified epoxy is measured as 159 °C, in agreement with the literature [18]. No significant change in the glass transition temperature was observed with the addition of CSR particles and nanosilica particles, see Figure 8. This indicates that the CSR particles remain phase-separated as expected.

Figure 8: Glass transition temperature, T_g , versus nanosilica content for (a) all the MX156 CSR particle-modified epoxies (b) all the MX960 CSR particle-modified epoxies.

4 MODELLING STUDIES

4.1 Description of the model

Figure 9 (a) shows a representative element composed by an epoxy matrix cylinder with a spherical nanosilica particle embedded inside. Because of symmetry, only half of the cylinder was modelled. The boundary conditions and mesh are shown in Figure 9 (b). The mean diameter of nanosilica is 20 nm and the epoxy was modified with 10% volume fraction of particles (i.e. 14.95 wt %).

The epoxy matrix was modelled using von Mises plasticity. The experimental stress-strain curve was used to model the non-linear response of the epoxy matrix, see Figure 3. The nanosilica was modelled as an isotropic linear-elastic material. The input mechanical properties for the epoxy matrix and the nanosilica are listed in Table 3.

Figure 9: (a) unit-cell used in the FEM, (b) boundary conditions and mesh of the axisymmetric model.

A 0.1 nm thick layer of cohesive elements was applied between the nanosilica and the epoxy matrix to model the cohesive forces under triaxial tensile loading. The cohesive interaction was modelled assuming a bilinear traction-separation law [20]. As a first approximation, the traction-separation parameters (stiffness, strength and fracture energy) were considered to be the same as for the unmodified epoxy (see Table 4). Damage initiation was modelled assuming a quadratic nominal stress criterion, and damage evolution was modelled using a quadratic fracture criterion [21].

Table 3: Material properties for the epoxy matrix and nanosilica.
Nanosilica properties are obtained from literature [22].

Materials	Young's modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio
Epoxy	2.87	0.35
Nanosilica	70	0.21

Table 4: Properties of cohesive elements used for the modelling.

	Stiffness (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Fracture energy (J/m ²)
Normal mode	2.87	87.56	78.3
Shear mode	1.06	48.16	78.3

4.2 Modelling results

Figure 10 shows the results from the finite element simulation of the toughening mechanisms of nanosilica-reinforced epoxy. The sequence of events predicted is (Figure 10 (a)):

1. Onset of plasticity of the epoxy matrix (point A on the stress-strain graph), originating at the nanosilica-epoxy interface;
2. Progressive degradation of the interface between the nanosilica and the epoxy matrix;
3. After reaching the peak load (point B), the stress-strain curve is showing the anticipated strain softening behavior, with progressive opening of the particle-epoxy interface (see point C).

Figure 10 (b) shows the predicted energy dissipation due to nanoparticle debonding and the energy dissipation due to the plastic deformation of the epoxy matrix. This indicates that the toughness improvement of nanosilica-modified epoxy is a combination of nanoparticle debonding and plastic deformation of the epoxy matrix, which agrees well with the literature [10]. It is evident from the graph (10 (b)) that plastic deformation of the epoxy matrix is the dominant contributor to the toughness improvement of the nanosilica-modified anhydride cured DGEBA epoxy, which is in good agreement with the experimental work of Masania [8].

Figure 10: The sequence of events and overall response predicted from the finite element analysis of nanosilica toughening mechanisms.

5 CONCLUSIONS

An anhydride cured DGEBA epoxy has been modified using hybrid combinations of 100 nm/300 nm diameter core-shell rubber (CSR) particles and nanosilica particles with varying weight percentages. The Young's modulus, fracture toughness, yield behavior and glass transition temperature have been determined for the unmodified and modified epoxies, and the hybrid toughening effect has been investigated. The results obtained were compared with the literature. The fracture toughness of modified epoxy can be increased to 592 J/m² by the combination of 9 wt% of MX156 CSR particles and 9 wt% of nanosilica, without a loss of the Young's modulus. CSR particle cavitation has been clearly identified from the SEM micrographs.

The failure and toughening mechanisms of particle-reinforced epoxies have been investigated by FE modelling. An axisymmetric analysis was performed, considering an elastic nanosilica particle embedded in a non-linear plastic epoxy matrix, with a cohesive interface, under triaxial tension. Plastic deformation and nanosilica debonding were identified as the main toughening mechanisms of nanosilica-modified epoxies. Further modelling will be performed to investigate the effect of varying the cohesive parameters and the plasticity criterion of the epoxy matrix.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kinloch AJ, Lee JH, Taylor AC, Sprenger S, Eger C, Egan D. Toughening structural adhesives via nano- and micro-phase inclusions. *Journal of Adhesion* 2003; 79(8-9):867-73.

- [2] Sultan JN, McGarry FJ. Effect of rubber particle-size on deformation mechanisms in glassy epoxy. *Polymer Engineering and Science* 1973;13(1):29-34.
- [3] Giannakopoulos G, Masania K, Taylor AC. Toughening of epoxy using core-shell particles. *Journal of Materials Science* 2011; 46(2):327-38.
- [4] Kinloch AJ, Yuen ML, Jenkins SD. Thermoplastic-toughened epoxy polymers. *Journal of Materials Science* 1994;29(14):3781-90.
- [5] Spanoudakis J, Young RJ. Crack-propagation in a glass particle-filled epoxy-resin. Part1: Effect of particle-volume fraction and size. *Journal of Materials Science* 1984;19(2):473-86.
- [6] Hsieh TH, Kinloch AJ, Masania K, Lee JS, Taylor AC, Sprenger S. The toughness of epoxy polymers and fibre composites modified with rubber microparticles and silica nanoparticles. *Journal of Materials Science* 2010;45(5):1193-210.
- [7] Kinloch AJ, Mohammed RD, Taylor AC, Eger C, Sprenger S, Egan D. The effect of silica nano particles and rubber particles on the toughness of multiphase thermosetting epoxy polymers. *Journal of Materials Science* 2005;40(18):5083-6.
- [8] Masania K. *Toughening mechanisms of silica nanoparticle-modified epoxy polymers*, PhD thesis, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Imperial College London; London, 2010.
- [9] Giannakopoulos G, Masania K, Taylor AC. Toughening of epoxy using core-shell particles. *Journal of Materials Science* 2011;46(2):327-38.
- [10] Guild FJ, Kinloch AJ. Modeling the properties of rubber-modified epoxy polymers. *Journal of Materials Science* 1995;30(7):1689-97.
- [11] Bray DJ, Dittanet P, Guild FJ, Kinloch AJ, Masania K, Pearson RA, et al. The modelling of the toughening of epoxy polymers via silica nanoparticles: The effects of volume fraction and particle size. *Polymer*. 2013;54(26):7022-32.
- [12] Kaneka Belgium. [online]. Available from: <http://www.kaneka.be> [Accessed July 2014].
- [13] Evonick Industries. [online]. Available from: <http://www.corporate.evonik.com> [Accessed July 2014].
- [14] ISO-527-1, *Plastics-determination of tensile properties-part 1: General principles*, International Standards Organizations: Geneva 1993.
- [15] ISO-527-2. *Plastics-determination of tensile properties-part 2: Test conditions for moulding and extrusion plastics*. International Standards Organization: Geneva 1996.
- [16] Williams JG, Ford H. Stress-strain relationships for some unreinforced plastics. *Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science* 1964; 6:405-17.
- [17] ISO-13586. *Plastics-determination of fracture toughness (G_{IC} and K_{IC})-Linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) approach*. International Standards Organization: Geneva 2000.
- [18] Chong HM, Taylor AC. The microstructure and fracture performance of styrene-butadiene-methylmethacrylate block copolymer-modified epoxy polymers. *Journal of Materials Science* 2013; 48 (19):6762-77.
- [19] Pukánszky B, Vörös G. Stress distribution around inclusions, interaction, and mechanical properties of particulate-filled composites. *Polymer Composites* 1996;17(3):384-92.
- [20] Alfano M, Furgiuele F, Leonardi A, Maletta C, Paulino GH. Cohesive zone modeling of mode I fracture in adhesive bonded joints. *Key Engineering Materials* Vols. 348-349 (2007) pp. 13-16.
- [21] Dassault Systemes Simulia Corp. Abaqus Analysis 6.13, User's Manual, 2013.
- [22] Guild FJ, Young RJ. A predictive model for particulate-filled composite-materials. Part 1: Hard particles. *Journal of Materials Science* 1989;24(1):298-306.